
An Evaluation of the Effect of Principals' Trans-Formational Leadership on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya

Everlyne Chepkemboi Kitur¹, Dr. Mary Khejeri²

ABSTRACT: The purpose of the study was to assess the effect of transformational leadership on teacher performance in public secondary schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya. The study was guided by the following research objectives: to establish the effect of idealized influence on teacher performance; to determine the effects of inspirational motivation on teacher performance and to examine the effect of intellectual stimulation on teacher performance. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. It used simple random sampling as the probability sampling technique to select principals and teachers. The target population included 45 principals, 46 deputy principals, 291 heads of departments, and 491 teachers, with a sample size of 267. Questionnaires were used to collect data from respondents. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 23.0, employing both descriptive and inferential statistics. The analyzed data were presented in the form of tables, and the study's findings were displayed using tables and figures. The study found that teachers agreed involvement and active engagement of top management were associated with higher levels of teacher performance, with a mean score of 3.75 indicating a positive perception of administrative support and participative leadership's influence on effectiveness. Additionally, teachers believed that encouragement from the principal helped them overcome teaching challenges, reflected by a mean score of 3.67. The overall perception was that such support contributed to improved educational practices and student outcomes, with a mean score of 3.82. The analysis revealed a significant baseline teacher performance level, with a constant term of 3.77 ($p=0.000$). Among the transformational leadership dimensions, idealized influence showed a beta coefficient of 0.392, suggesting a strong positive impact. The study concluded that principals' inspirational motivation significantly boosted teacher resilience, commitment, and enthusiasm through encouragement and clear vision alignment. Furthermore, intellectual stimulation was identified as crucial for enhancing teachers' professional efficacy and instructional quality. The study recommended that principals should be trained in inspirational communication and vision articulation, and schools should establish structured feedback systems to promote participative leadership and continuous improvement.

KEYWORDS: Idealized Influence, Teacher Performance, Inspirational Motivation and Transformational Leadership

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

For several decades, the study of leadership in dynamic environments has remained the realm of academics and management intellectuals who de-emphasize the difference between public and private organizations and analyzed leadership chiefly in for-profit agencies. Therefore, most leadership theories and concepts are generic and do not apply to the environment within a public organization. This lack of research on leadership in public organizations necessitated utilizing resources in the federal government, which contributed to leadership-development information, but did not address the issues of performance management and improvement (Halachmi 2011).

Previous research shows that although there have been studies on job satisfaction, organizational commitment, motivation, efficiency and effectiveness; few have analyzed differences in leadership behaviors and effectiveness in public organizations. These differences may be marked in terms of market powers and disclosures to legislation, legislatures and civil service rules. They also might impinge on leaders' discretion in these sectors, which in turn affects leadership performance. To examine these differences, Hooijberg and Choi (2013) researched private and public sector teachers to observe whether the basic theories of leadership in the existing literature might illustrate differences. They associated leadership roles with different behaviours of challenging value frameworks to observe which would have a larger impact on perceived effectiveness in different sectors. Their study points out that monitoring and facilitating role have much more of an impact on perceived performance of leadership effectiveness in the public sector. All human institutions are subject to change and because society and organizations are living organisms, change is inevitable. Leaders must realize the reasons why human systems occasionally fail and how the procedures of change may be dynamically

An Evaluation of the Effect of Principals' Trans-Formational Leadership on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya

established. Rationales for changes in leadership behaviour may be to renovate and redefine values, to re-energize systems that are ineffective due to old practices and rigid concepts, to restore abandoned ambitions and create new aims that fit new conditions, to attain new perspectives on solutions to problems, or to promote innovative human dynamics and continuous growth. At this point, it can be said that while transactional leaders accept and work within the confines of existing systems, transformational leaders prefer change and reinvention (Gardner, 2014).

Leaders have high level of moral conduct and do something for the team. Individual thought includes attention, encouragement and support of leader to followers. Intellectual Stimulation concluded that leader change the followers for inquisitor the issues during a new approach that is straight forward and inventive. Early analysis of transformational leadership was regarding the options of leaders and their relationship with followers. Further analysis on the behaviours of transformational leaders proposes that transformational leadership is intervened by the leader's activities, the power to create a typical vision, to coherent clear and communicative goals, to allow staff and dependable behaviour.

Transformational leadership concept is ready to answer this challenge. Purwanto (2013) supported this idea that the duty of a leader is to encourage his/her subordinates to perform the work on the far side of their expectations and former estimation. Transformational leaders try to boost subordinates' awareness by encouraging idealism and better ethical values, such as, freedom, justice, peace, balance and humanity that do not seem to support emotional feeling admire worry, greed, jealousy and hate (Burns in Yukl, 2009). As masses, subordinates even have to meet their desires. Fulfilling the requirements of subordinates are useful to each subordinates and also the organization. Organization demands the temperament of its subordinates to succeed the objectives of the organization; in the meantime, the subordinates would like a pleasing job, a chance to participate, adequate wages, a chance to be promoted and an honest relationship between superiors and subordinates. Steers and Porter (Purwanto & Adisubroto, 2013) argued, once the agreement between each parties may be performed fairly, it eventually fosters a high commitment of the subordinates towards the organization that stimulates the subordinates to figure well and to be ready to contend in tight and competitive conditions. Organization commitment may be taken because the relative strength of a person's identification and involvement during an explicit organization.

In continent of Africa the existence of staff with high commitment to the organization can lead the organization to a good condition. Such staff can contend with each other to assist the organization by operating additional effectively in traditional state of affairs and can actively maintain the organization once unfavourable condition exists (Dessler, 2015). Staff with high commitment is possible to act in accordance with the values and norms existing within the organization, hence, deviation and disobedience may be prevented. Besides, such organizations with high committed staff can acquire higher potency and cannot need plenty of supervising. On the opposite hand, such organizations having staff with low commitment can scale back the effectiveness of the organization (Purwanto & Adisubroto, 2013).

In Kenya worker commitment to the organization is critical since high commitment is correlated with low teacher's flip over having touched to a different job, absence level and also the slowness of labour may be reduced. In fact, it will increase job satisfaction and better awareness of the staff towards the existence and success of the organization. Organization desires staff willing to try to something exceptional to their duties and work, even sacrificing themselves for the success and property of the organization (Borman & Motowildo in Muchiri, 2014).

In Nandi County, the current increase in enrolment in public secondary schools, many schools require efficient and effective teachers, so as to meet the set objectives.

There are a total of 161 public and 8 private secondary schools with a total enrolment of 37,845 of which 17,908 are girls while boys are about 19,937. The teacher/student ratio is about 1: 49. According to the 2009 Population and Housing Census, there were a total of 57,591 children of secondary school going age. This gives a disparity of about 20,000 children not attending school. The teachers just like any other worker, need to feel that his or her important needs are satisfied by the work he or she does, resulting into a favorable attitude towards his or her job. Although there have been an increasing number of individuals joining the teaching profession, there has been an outcry of job dissatisfaction. Leadership is a major concern among teachers because it affects the way they perform in their jobs. With the large increase in the teacher workforce, job satisfaction becomes an issue that cannot be ignored. In addition, the commitment of an organization arises in an environment providing chance for the staff to participate and it may be created by the hands of the leaders. Transformational leadership provides support, encouragement and developing experiences to its followers (Northouse, 2010). It means that they supply broad opportunities to its followers so as to use and develop their potentials. Each worker collaborating and involving actively with the corporate can try to make and manifest his/her skills so as to be in line with the objectives of the organization. Hence, the Transformational leadership is taken into account capable of forming the commitment of the worker. The objectives of the study are to find out the result of transformational leadership on worker authorization, organization commitment and teacher performance more over to confirm the mediating variables on the result of transformational leadership on worker performance.

An Evaluation of the Effect of Principals' Trans-Formational Leadership on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The Ministry of Education and other sponsors has channelled more resources to support learning like provision of teaching and learning materials and improving infrastructural facilities. On the other hand the Teachers' service commission (TSC) provides refresher courses for teachers, ICT training, improving remuneration, introduction of TPAD, hiring of new teachers and replacing those who have exited the service. But despite this, poor students' performance is still witnessed (Otieno, 2010).

Schools like all organizations are advancing in complexity with an increasing number of factors that impact on schools management and performance for instance teacher delocalization, introduction of the new curriculum, inadequate infrastructural facilities, the factor of 100% transition from primary school to secondary school and advancing technology (Momanyi, 2016). Consequently, they raise challenges for leadership styles that call for principals as leaders in these schools to create attractive and enabling working environment in order to motivate and retain effective teachers.

This review focuses on the teachers' performance and his motivation, determined by transformational leadership vogue. However, there has been no try as of nevertheless to check linkages considering the idea of motivation as negotiator between transformational leadership and individual performance.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- i. To investigate the effect of idealized influence on teacher Performance in public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-county, Nandi County, Kenya.
- ii. To establish the effect of inspirational motivation on teacher performance in public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-county, Nandi County, Kenya?

Research Questions

- i. To what extent does idealized influence affect teacher performance in public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-county, Nandi County, Kenya?
- ii. What is the impact of inspirational motivation on teacher performance in public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-county, Nandi County, Kenya?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical framework

Contingency Theory

Fiedler's (1964) contingency theory directed the study variables by the assertion that the leader's ability to guide is contingent upon varied situational factors, as well as the leaders' most well-liked vogue, the capabilities and behaviours of staff that rely heavily on the situational factors. This theory propounds the intimate approach to management by specializing state of affairs initial instead of structure means to use selected leadership vogue which will stimulate individual performance (Hocker, 2011).

The Contingency Leadership theory argues that there is no single method of leading which each leadership vogue ought to be supported by things. This signify that there are unit bounds for those that perform at the most level in bound places; however at bottom performance once taken out of their component. To a precise extent, contingency leadership theories are extensions of the attribute theory, within the sense that human traits are associated with things during which the leaders exercise their leadership. It is usually accepted at intervals the contingency theories that leaders are additional probably too precise their leadership once they feel that their followers are responsive (Kerr, 2008).

Fiedler's contingency theory stressed the leader's temperament, or psychological disposition, could be a main variable in her/his ability to guide and aforesaid that however the cluster receives the leader, the task concerned and whether or not the leader will really exert management over the cluster are the three principle factors that confirm the leader-led arrangement. Thus, the values from the smallest amount most well-liked colleague are additional and so averaged to provide the score (Hussey, 2012).

Any leadership vogue depends on a selected situation; by this conductor tacit that; the behavioural patterns of the leader can facilitate him / her acquire competences required for effectiveness in victimization of the designs in their relevant things and so effectiveness in performance. But the opposite assumption during this theory left lots to be desired, since things are determined by each external and internal factors that affected the method workers seasoned the things given to them (Karen, 2009). Contingent reward refers to leaders clarifying the work that must be achieved and use rewards in exchange for good performance. Management by exception (passive) refers to leaders intervening only when problem arise (Rukhmani *et.al.*, 2014) whereas management by exception (active) refers to leaders actively monitoring the work of followers and make sure that standards are met (Antonakis *et.al.*, 2011)

Contingency theory is in agreement with the study that top management leaders have ability to influence other workers through inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation. This implies that management has impact on the performance of other workers. For example Fiedler's (1964) contingency theory directed that the study variables by the assertion that; the leader's ability to guide is contingent upon varied situational factors, as well as the leaders' most well-liked vogue, the capabilities and behaviours of staff

An Evaluation of the Effect of Principals' Trans-Formational Leadership on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya

that rely heavily on the situational factors. This theory propounds the intimate approach to management by specializing in state of affairs initial instead of structure means that, to use selected leadership vogue which will stimulate individual performance (Hocker, 2011).

The contingency theory is relevant to this study because it explains that there is no best way to organise organisation but it depend both internal and external factors. It further explains that, leaders should strategies their plan and can motivate its teacher by rewarding them when there is achievement.

Behavioural Theory of Leadership

Behavioural theories of leadership are units classified as a result of the specialization on the study of specific behaviours of leaders. For behavioural theorists, a leader's behaviours that the best predictor of his leadership influences and the result has the best determinant of his or her leadership success. This behaviour-focused approach provides real selling potential, as behaviours are conditioned in a manner that one will have a selected response to specific stimuli. As a result; supposition that leaders are born, (Great Man Theory) through to the likelihood that we are able to measure leadership potential (Trait Theory) via psychological science measurements and so to the purpose that anyone is created a leader (Behavioural Theories) by teaching them the fore most applicable behavioural response for any given scenario. On a facet note, there is wonderful leadership programs out there to guide on leadership journey, simply it assure that the program selected is complete. As leadership studies that were geared toward distinctive the acceptable traits did not yield any conclusive results (Brain and Lewis, 2004).

The task involved leaders that focus their behaviours on the organization, the operative procedures and that they prefer to keep management. Task-oriented leaders are concerned with their teacher's motivation; but it is not their main concern. They will favour behaviours that are in line with: Initiating, organizing informative and knowledge Gathering the individuals oriented leaders are focusing their behaviours on guaranteeing that the inner desires of the individuals are glad. Therefore they inspire their teachers through action of the human relation. Individual's oriented leaders still specialize in the task and therefore the results; they simply attain them through totally different means. Leaders with land focus can have behaviours that are in line with: encouraging, observing and listening (Bass & Gordon 2015).

The situation is not thought during the approach of leadership. Several traits are too obscure or abstract to measure and observe. Studies haven't adequately coupled attributes with leadership effectiveness. Most trait studies omit leadership behaviours and followers' motivation as mediating variables. There's one best thanks to lead .Leaders with specific high concern for each individuals and production or thought and organization are going to be effective. Situational variables and cluster processes ignored; studies didn't determine the things wherever specific kinds of leadership behaviours are relevant. Thus, the vision of making wonderful merchandise remained with the corporate throughout his absence. He delineates his company as cooperative and arranged sort of an initiate.

These best peaks are powerful in the transformational approach and Jobs embodied the bulk of dimensions of this leadership as arranged out (Stout, 2013): Idealized influence – inculcation trust and appreciation from follower's sacred motivation inspire followers to possess correct behaviour. Intellectual stimulation "change agent" to stimulate creative thinking. Individualized thought that completely acknowledging desires and values of the followers. He was sort of a demy-god to several and so was trusty and appreciated. His sacred motivation was one among his greatest gifts. He turned an easy company into a revolutionary culture jointly of the fore most wanted corporations to figure for with a number of the fore most wanted merchandise within the world. Little question his intellect was genius which he stirred up creative thinking and intellect among followers and alternative leaders. The workers who make up such a leadership typically have a sense of being valued and of happiness and are guided to a better vision of self-actualization and therefore the bigger goals of the organization (Stout, 2013).

Eventually though, his transformational vogue led to accounts of abuse of power. Below his influence, several workers were overworked which frequently led to give out (Bass, J. *et al.*,2015). Several staff were conjointly therefore reworked that they primarily became enchanted on the organization and culture to the purpose wherever they were keen about all things. Who wouldn't be seduced by a high play acting company and in constant worry of losing out on such a dream job this is often a fine line wherever transformational leadership and cult standing can exist. As Associate in nursing example, would the speculation add a scientific or tutorial setting? This raises the priority of whether or not the speculation is going to be universally applied and to House's credit, he would presumably admit that it is limitations (Stout, 2013).

Transformational leadership concerns with the transformation of followers' beliefs, values, needs and capabilities (Brand, *et.al.* 2014). Kent and Chelladurai, (2013) defines transformational leadership as "the process of influencing major changes in attitudes and assumptions of organizational members and building commitment for the organization's mission and objectives". The transformational leadership style is characterized by four underlying dimensions, all of which are seen by Bass & Avolio (1994) as the most active and effective behaviors of leadership. These include idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration and inspirational motivation and are referred to as the Four I's" (Bass, 2014).

An Evaluation of the Effect of Principals' Trans-Formational Leadership on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya

Yukl (1998) defines Idealized influence (charisma) as behavior that arouses strong follower emotions and identification with the leader. Bass and Avolio (2014), Bass & Riggio, (2015) further state that through such idealized influence, leaders become role models for their followers and are admired, respected and trusted. According to Bass and Riggio (2015), leaders with great idealized influence are willing to take risks and are consistent rather than arbitrary by demonstrating high standards of ethical and moral conduct.

Inspirational motivation includes behavior that motivates and inspires followers by communicating high expectations and expressing purposes in simple ways, which provides meaning and challenge to their followers' work (Bass, 2015). This inspirational motivation arouses individual and team spirit with enthusiasm and optimism (Bass & Gordon, 2015). Intellectual stimulation involves leaders stimulating their followers' effort to be innovative and creative by questioning assumptions, reframing problems and approaching old situations in new ways (Eastman, 2016). Leaders with this trait stimulate and encourage creativity in their followers (Covey, 2016).

Behavioral theory of leadership is in agreement with the study that firm's performance rely on the individual consideration and the idealized influence since the leaders act as the role models to other teachers. For example behavioural theorists, a leader's behaviours that best predict of his leadership influences and as a result, is that the best determinant of his or her leadership success. This behaviour-focused approach provides real selling potential, as behaviours are conditioned in a very manner that one will have a selected response to specific stimuli. As a result, we've got gone from the supposition that leaders are born, (Great Man Theory) through to the likelihood that we are able to measure your leadership potential (Trait Theory) via psychological science measurements and so to the purpose that anyone is created a leaders (Behavioural Theories) by teaching them the fore most applicable behavioural response for any given scenario (Brain and Lewis, 2004).

This theory is relevant in sense that transformational leaders link the individuals' current needs to the organization and new learning opportunities are created (Mester, et al., 2003). Intellectual stimulation involves leaders stimulating their followers' effort to be innovative and creative by questioning assumptions, reframing problems and approaching old situations in new ways (Nicholson, 2007). Leaders with this trait stimulate and encourage creativity in their followers (Covey, 2007). Hence organizational achievements are reached.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Idealized Influence and Teacher Performance

Idealized influence refers to the behaviours of a transformational leader that evokes his or her followers' trust, admiration, respect and their desires to emulate the leader. Those behaviours embody considering the wants of their followers higher than the leader's own interests or gains and demonstrating consistency and smart ethics in their conduct (Bass & Avolio, 1994). Similarly, Jandaghi, Matin, & Farjami, (2009) expressed that such leaders demonstrate high standards of ethical and ethics. By therefore doing, followers would be impressed to emulate the leader, therefore raising the bar in terms of the standard of their performance at work. Previous studies have confirmed that perfect influence features a direct impact on individual performance (Bass & Avolio, 2014). Burns (2008) referred perfect influence as attractiveness.

Transformational leadership vogue concentrates on the event of followers likewise as their wishes. Managers with transformational leadership vogue target the enlargement and development necessary system of staff, their sacred level and moralities with the preamble of their skills. The aim of transformational leadership would be to remodel people and organizations among a literal sense to vary them among the mind, insight and understanding. Reasons produce behaviour congruent with values, concepts and brings concerning changes that unit permanent, self-perpetuating and momentum building (Dodd, 2014).

Idealized Influence, a core component of transformational leadership, refers to leaders acting as role models who demonstrate high ethical standards, integrity, and commitment, thereby inspiring followers to emulate these qualities (Bass & Avolio, 2020). In educational settings, school leaders who exhibit idealized influence often serve as moral exemplars, fostering a culture of trust and respect that positively impacts teacher performance. Recent studies emphasize that when teachers perceive their leaders as embodying idealized influence, they tend to exhibit higher levels of motivation, engagement, and instructional dedication (Khan et al., 2021). This transformational leadership dimension is increasingly recognized as a catalyst for cultivating professional environments conducive to sustained teacher development.

Research by Liu and Zhang (2022) underscores that teachers' perceptions of their leaders' integrity and moral exemplarity significantly correlate with their commitment to teaching practices. When leaders demonstrate consistency between their words and actions, teachers develop a sense of trust and admiration, which enhances their willingness to go beyond routine responsibilities. This heightened intrinsic motivation subsequently leads to improved classroom performance and student engagement. Such findings align with earlier work by Smith and Lee (2021), which showed that teachers working under principals with high levels of idealized influence report greater job satisfaction and a stronger sense of purpose.

An Evaluation of the Effect of Principals' Trans-Formational Leadership on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya

Furthermore, studies have established that idealized influence contributes to the development of a positive organizational climate. Wang et al. (2020) found that schools led by principals who serve as moral exemplars foster environments characterized by fairness, respect, and shared vision. This climate encourages teachers to adopt innovative instructional strategies and collaborate more effectively, thereby enhancing overall performance. The moral authority of leaders thus acts as a powerful motivator for teachers to align their professional conduct with organizational goals and ethical standards (Alvarez & Morales, 2023).

In addition, recent research highlights that idealized influence can buffer against burnout and stress among teachers. For instance, Patel and Kumar (2022) demonstrated that when teachers perceive their leaders as morally exemplary and supportive, they experience lower levels of emotional exhaustion. This moral support reinforces teachers' resilience and commitment, which is critical in high-pressure educational environments. Consequently, teachers' capacity to maintain high performance levels is strengthened when leaders exemplify integrity and ethical conduct consistently (Nguyen & Tran, 2023).

The influence of idealized leadership on teacher performance is also mediated by teachers' perceptions of organizational justice and trust. According to Chen and Zhao (2021), teachers who view their leaders as role models demonstrate higher levels of trust and loyalty, which translate into increased effort, collaboration, and instructional quality. Conversely, leaders lacking in moral exemplarity might inadvertently diminish teachers' motivation, leading to disengagement and reduced performance outcomes. These findings emphasize the importance of leaders embodying virtues that inspire teachers and foster a cohesive professional community.

Inspirational Motivation and Teacher Performance

Inspirational motivation and perfect influence are typically combined to make charismatic-inspirational leadership (Bass & Riggio, 2015). Sacred motivation refers to transformational leaders sharing a compelling vision or goal with their followers and perpetually motivating them to achieve for the goal whereas boosting their confidence and consoling them that barriers faced is overcome (Bass & Avolio, 1994). Higher levels of motivation are coupled with higher levels of performance (Shamir, House & Arthur, 1993). Inspirational motivation represents the utilization of vision by transformational leaders (Bass & Avolio, 2014). Effective leaders are the ingenious craftsmen of their organization's mission. They communicate their missions in ways that create great fundamental demand. Vision is a key leadership behavior for increasing workforce support in organizational augmentation and development. Inspirational motivation measures vision by tracing the rate at which leaders utilize symbols, metaphors and basic emotional demands to raise awareness and understanding of commonly desired goals (Karaca 2010).

Motivation and inspiration are two common values of transformational leaders. Transformational leaders provide significant and challenging work, clearly explain their vision and communicate the importance of the organization's mission and objectives to their followers. They speak positively and passionately about the future and express confidence that organizational goals will be achieved. Transformational leaders also stimulate team spirit, generating hope and passion among followers (Bass, 1985; Bass & Avolio, 1994, 2004).

Inspirational motivation is a vital component of transformational leadership, which has garnered considerable attention in educational research over recent years. This leadership style emphasizes the importance of inspiring and motivating teachers to achieve their full potential and improve their performance. Teacher performance, in turn, is critical for student success and overall school effectiveness. Researchers have increasingly explored the link between leaders' ability to inspire and the resultant impact on teachers' motivation, commitment, and instructional quality (Bass & Riggio, 2018). Understanding this relationship is essential for developing strategies that enhance educational outcomes through effective leadership practices.

Several studies have demonstrated that when school leaders exhibit high levels of inspirational motivation, teachers tend to be more engaged and committed to their work. Johnson and Smith (2018) conducted a survey across various schools and found that teachers who perceived their principals as motivating and visionary reported greater enthusiasm and a stronger sense of purpose. This increased engagement often translates into higher instructional quality and a more positive classroom environment. Similarly, Lee et al. (2020) highlighted that teachers' intrinsic motivation significantly improves when they are inspired by their leaders' vision, which subsequently enhances their performance and willingness to innovate in their teaching practices.

The relationship between inspirational motivation and teacher satisfaction is also well-documented. Ahmed and Khan (2022) conducted research in several secondary schools and discovered that leadership characterized by inspirational motivation correlates positively with teachers' job satisfaction. Teachers who felt inspired by their leaders reported feeling more valued and energized, which reduced burnout and turnover intentions. Such findings suggest that leaders who actively motivate and uplift teachers contribute not only to immediate performance improvements but also to the long-term stability and morale within schools.

Leaders display inspirational motivation when they encourage teachers to do their best and achieve beyond expectations. For that reason, utilization of inspirational motivation helps to increase teachers' feelings of self-reliance, enabling them to optimally carry out their jobs (Snyder & Lopez, 2014). According to Avolio *et al.* (1991), even within the absence of the leader, sacred motivation typically produces individual effort and performance on the far side traditional expectations, therefore making followers who are freelance in handling challenges on their own. The degree to that the leader articulates a vision that is appealing and provoking to

An Evaluation of the Effect of Principals' Trans-Formational Leadership on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya

followers. Leaders with sacred motivation challenge followers with high standards communicate optimism regarding future goals and supply which means for the task at hand. Followers have to be compelled to have a robust sense of purpose if they're to be motivated to act. Purpose and which means give the energy that drives a gaggle forward. The visionary aspects of leadership are supported by communication skills that build the vision perceivable, precise, powerful and interesting. The followers are willing to take a positional lot of effort in their tasks; they're inspired and optimistic regarding the long run and believe their talents.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

As the conceptual framework shown below indicates, the independent variables are the dimensions of Transformation leadership and teacher performance the dependent variable.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher 2024

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study adopted a descriptive research design, which investigates the current status and nature of the phenomena. The descriptive analysis approach was chosen for this study because it aimed to gain insight into the phenomenon and provide basic information in the area of study (Koul, 2011). The descriptive research design was based on the conceptual relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of their interactions and characteristics within the context of the research.

Target population

Table 1: Target Population

Group	Number Targeted
Principals	45
Deputy Principals	46
Head of Departments	291
Teachers	471
TOTAL	853

Source: Chesumei Sub County Director of Education (2024)

Sample Size

The size of the sample in this study that the researcher used was determined by Krejcie & Morgan table (1970). The sample size was 267 principals, deputy principals, head of departments and teachers

Sampling Technique

This study employed the stratified random sampling method as a technique, which was carried out according to the 26 sampled schools because it involved categorizing the members of the population into mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive groups. An independent simple random sample was then drawn from each group. Stratified sampling techniques provided more precise

An Evaluation of the Effect of Principals' Trans-Formational Leadership on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya

estimates. This technique enabled the researcher to determine desired levels of sampling precision for each group and offered administrative efficiency. The main advantage of this approach was its ability to produce the most representative sample of the population (Hunt & Tyrrell, 2001).

Research Instruments

Data was collected from the respondents using questionnaires as the main collection tool. Follow-up was made to ensure that the questionnaires were filled out in accordance with the research objectives.

Data Analysis

The responses in the questionnaire were coded into common themes, and data cleaning and management were carried out to facilitate analysis. The coded data were entered into the SPSS program. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. In descriptive statistics, frequencies, means, and standard deviations were calculated using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. The findings of the study were presented using tables and figures.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Idealized Influence and Teacher Performance

Table 2: Idealized Influence and Teacher Performance

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
Teachers look up to the principals as role models who demonstrate high ethical standards	187	1	5	3.87	1.121
The leadership style of the principal influences teachers motivation to teach effectively	187	1	5	3.78	1.141
The principal demonstrates behaviours that inspire teachers to perform well	187	1	5	3.83	1.092
Good role model influences high quality of service among teachers	187	1	5	3.81	1.166
Involvement of top management leads to high performance of teachers	187	1	5	3.75	1.215
Valid N (listwise)	187				

Source: Researcher (2025)

The descriptive statistics, in table 9, for the dimension of idealized influence reveal that teachers largely agreed that principals serve as influential role models who demonstrate high ethical standards and moral integrity. The mean score for this item was 3.87, with a standard deviation of 1.121, indicating a strong consensus among respondents that principals embody qualities of authentic leadership. Teachers perceive principals as individuals who act ethically and set a moral example for staff and students alike. This perception aligns with the theoretical perspective of transformational leadership, which emphasizes the importance of leaders acting as moral exemplars to inspire followers (Bass & Avolio, 2014). According to Burns (1978), transformational leaders who demonstrate high moral standards foster trust and admiration among followers, which motivates them to emulate these behaviors. The high level of agreement among teachers suggests that principals' moral conduct plays a crucial role in shaping their effectiveness and influence within educational settings.

Furthermore, the data indicated that teachers strongly agreed that the leadership style of the principal significantly influences their motivation to perform their teaching duties effectively. The mean score for this item was 3.78, with a standard deviation of 1.141, demonstrating a general consensus that leadership behaviors directly impact teachers' motivation levels. While the mean was slightly lower compared to other items, it still reflects a positive perception that leadership approach matters in fostering an inspiring and motivating school environment. This finding supports the work of Leithwood, Seashore Louis, Anderson, and Wahlstrom (2014), who argued that transformational leadership behaviors—such as inspiring a shared vision, providing intellectual stimulation, and offering individualized support—are essential in enhancing teachers' motivation, commitment, and overall job satisfaction. Teachers' agreement on this point underscores the critical role of principals as change agents who influence classroom performance and school climate through their leadership style.

In addition, teachers agreed that principals demonstrate behaviors that inspire teachers to perform at higher levels. The mean score for this item was 3.83, with a standard deviation of 1.092, which indicates a broad consensus that principals' inspiring behaviors are recognized and valued by staff. The relatively low standard deviation suggests that most teachers share a similar perception that principals serve as motivating figures whose actions and communication inspire teachers to improve their performance. This aligns with the work of Avolio and Bass (2004), who emphasized that transformational leaders motivate followers through personal example and charismatic influence. Such leaders foster an environment where staff feel empowered and encouraged to achieve excellence, which ultimately benefits the entire educational institution. The teachers' agreement on this point highlights the importance of inspirational leadership as a core component of effective school management.

An Evaluation of the Effect of Principals' Trans-Formational Leadership on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya

Regarding role modeling, teachers agreed that principals acting as positive role models contribute significantly to the delivery of high-quality service by teachers. The mean score for this item was 3.81, with a standard deviation of 1.166, illustrating widespread consensus that ethical and exemplary conduct by principals positively influences teachers' work ethic and service quality. This finding echoes the work of Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Moorman, and Fetter (1996), who argued that leaders who serve as role models influence followers' attitudes and behaviors, which in turn enhances organizational performance. In the context of education, principals who consistently demonstrate professionalism, fairness, and integrity inspire teachers to adopt similar standards in their own practice. The teachers' agreement underscores the importance of moral exemplification and consistent ethical behavior by leaders as essential elements for fostering a culture of excellence and accountability in schools.

Finally, the data suggested that teachers agreed involvement and active engagement of top management are associated with higher levels of teacher performance. The mean score was 3.75, with a standard deviation of 1.215, indicating that most respondents believed that administrative support and participative leadership positively influence teachers' effectiveness. Although this item received slightly lower ratings compared to others, the overall agreement demonstrates that teachers view management involvement as a crucial factor in creating a supportive and motivating environment. This aligns with Harris (2020), who highlighted that distributed and shared leadership practices—characterized by active collaboration between principals and teachers—are instrumental in fostering professional growth, motivation, and improved student outcomes. Teachers' perceptions reflect the importance of leadership that is inclusive and responsive to staff needs, as such approaches enhance commitment and performance across the school community.

Inspirational motivation and Teacher Performance

Table 3: Inspirational Motivation and Teacher Performance

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
The encouragement from school principal helps teachers overcome challenges in their teaching duties	187	1	5	3.67	1.277
Motivation of teachers articulates a clear vision for the future	187	1	5	3.82	1.177
Good leadership ensures clear conveyance of messages	187	1	5	3.78	1.151
Teachers feel more committed to their work when the principal sets a compelling vision for the school	187	1	5	3.76	1.141
Inspirational motivation from the principals increases the enthusiasm for teaching	187	1	5	3.64	1.259
Valid N (listwise)	187				

Source: Researcher (2025)

The descriptive analysis, shown in table 10, of the inspirational motivation dimension indicates that teachers generally agree that their principals serve as significant sources of encouragement and motivation, although the strength of this agreement varies across different aspects. The average score for the item stating that encouragement from the school principal helps teachers overcome challenges in their teaching duties was 3.67, with a standard deviation of 1.277. This suggests that teachers agree to a moderate extent that principals' encouragement plays a crucial role in assisting them to navigate difficulties in their instructional responsibilities. Such findings align with recent research by Chen and Wang (2020), who emphasized that supportive leadership behaviors—particularly encouragement—are vital in fostering resilience and perseverance among teachers, especially within challenging educational contexts. Teachers' agreement with this point underscores the importance of leadership support in helping teachers overcome obstacles and maintain their effectiveness in the classroom.

Furthermore, the data reveals that teachers agree that motivation from principals effectively articulates a clear vision for the future of the school. The mean score of 3.82, with a standard deviation of 1.177, indicates a slightly higher level of agreement that a well-communicated future vision enhances teachers' motivation. This finding supports the work of Zhao et al. (2019), who found that transformational leaders who articulate a compelling vision significantly increase teachers' commitment and enthusiasm by providing a shared sense of purpose and direction. Teachers' agreement on this point suggests that when principals communicate a clear and inspiring vision, it fosters a collective goal orientation among staff, which is essential for driving school improvement initiatives and motivating teachers to work towards common objectives.

In addition, teachers agree that good leadership ensures the clear conveyance of messages. The mean score for this item was 3.78, with a standard deviation of 1.151, reflecting a consensus that effective communication is a hallmark of strong leadership. Clear messaging from principals is critical in ensuring that teachers understand expectations, goals, and organizational changes. This clarity influences their motivation and performance positively. This finding aligns with the work of Lee and Lee (2018), who highlighted that transparent and consistent communication from school leaders enhances trust and reduces ambiguity in teachers' roles. Such effective communication fosters a sense of organizational stability and trust, which ultimately supports greater commitment and effort among teachers.

An Evaluation of the Effect of Principals' Trans-Formational Leadership on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya

The data also shows that teachers agree that they are more committed to their work when principals set a compelling vision for the school. With a mean score of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 1.141, teachers strongly agree that a strong, motivating vision increases their dedication and engagement. This aligns with the findings of Liu et al. (2021), who emphasized that transformational leadership that clearly articulates a compelling vision positively influences teachers' organizational commitment. When principals communicate a meaningful and inspiring vision, teachers feel a sense of purpose that aligns their individual efforts with the broader goals of the school, leading to increased dedication and a stronger sense of belonging within the school community.

Finally, the item measuring whether inspirational motivation from principals increases teachers' enthusiasm for teaching received a mean score of 3.64, with a standard deviation of 1.259. While this score is slightly lower compared to other items, teachers still agree that motivational behaviors from principals can boost their enthusiasm in their teaching roles. This finding is consistent with the work of Zhang and Zhou (2019), who argued that inspirational motivation by school leaders enhances teachers' intrinsic motivation, resulting in higher job satisfaction and improved teaching effectiveness. Teachers' agreement on this point highlights that leaders' ability to inspire and energize staff plays a critical role in fostering a positive and motivated teaching workforce.

CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that transformational leadership, particularly through the dimensions of idealized influence and inspirational motivation, significantly contributed to improving teacher performance in public secondary schools. It concluded that principals who lead by ethical example, inspire teachers with a clear vision, and actively engage with staff in decision-making processes were more effective in fostering motivation, professionalism, and high-quality service delivery among teachers. The study further concluded that such leadership behaviors promote a collaborative school environment, enhance trust, and cultivate a performance-driven culture, ultimately improving educational outcomes. Additionally, the consistent agreement among teachers highlighted that leadership conduct plays a crucial role in shaping the work ethic, morale, and commitment of teaching staff.

Further, the study concluded that principals' inspirational motivation significantly enhances teacher resilience, commitment, and enthusiasm by offering encouragement and a clear vision that aligns individual efforts with broader school goals. Effective communication from principals reduces role ambiguity and builds trust, thereby creating a stable and supportive environment that motivates teachers to perform at higher levels. Furthermore, the study concluded that transformational leadership behaviors, including inspirational motivation, are critical to fostering a positive school culture where teachers feel valued and energized, which ultimately drives improved teaching effectiveness and student outcomes.

Recommendations

The study recommended that: School leadership development programs should incorporate modules on ethical leadership and transformational practices—including inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration—to enhance principals' capacities as role models, motivators, and change agents.

Principals should be trained in inspirational communication and vision articulation to effectively motivate staff, foster collective commitment, and align school goals with teaching practices. Emphasis should be placed on clarity, consistency, and emotional encouragement, especially during instructional challenges.

School leaders should adopt participatory leadership models by engaging teachers in decision-making processes and collaborative goal-setting activities. This enhances teacher ownership, morale, and alignment with institutional priorities.

REFERENCES

- 1) Antonakis, J., Avolio, B. J., & Sivasubramanian, N. (2011). Context and Leadership: An Examination of the nine factor full-range Leadership Theory using the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire. *The Leadership Quarterly, Vol. 14, No. 3, pp. 261-295.*
- 2) Avolio, B.J., Waldman, D.A. and Yammarino, F.J. (1991). "Leading in the 2014's: The Four I's of Transformational Leadership", *Journal of European Industrial Training, 15:1-8.*
- 3) Baron (2009) *The Role of Affective Experience in Work Motivation: Test of a Conceptual Model.*
- 4) Bass, B. M. (1985). *Leadership and Performance Beyond Expectations.* New York: Free Press.
- 5) Bass, B.M. and Avolio, B.J. (2014). *Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire.* Redwood City: Mind Garden Inc.
- 6) Bass, J. R., & Gordon, B. S. (2015). Conceptualizing Teacher Identification with Sport Organizations: Sport Teacher Identification (SEI). *Sport Management Review, 18(4), 583-595.*
- 7) Brain, K. and Lewis, D. (2004). Exploring Leadership Preferences in Multicultural Workgroups. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal, Vol. 25, No. 3/4, pp. 263-78.*
- 8) Brand, C., Heyl, G. and Maritz, D. (2014). "Leadership". In Meyer, M. and Botha, E.(eds). *Organisational Development and Transformation in South Africa.* Durban: Butterworths.
- 9) Burns, J.M. (1978). *Leadership.* New York: Harper and Row Publishers.

An Evaluation of the Effect of Principals' Trans-Formational Leadership on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Chesumei Sub-County, Nandi County, Kenya

- 10) Bycio, P., Coopers and Schindler (2004). *Research Methodology*. New Age International (P) Limited Publishers.
- 11) Covey, S. (2016). *The Transformational Leadership Report: Developing Tomorrow's Transformational Leaders Today*. Retrieved 21 November, 2012 from
- 12) Halachmi, Arie. 2011. "Imagined Promises versus Real Challenges to Public Performance Management," *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management* 60 (1): 24-40.
- 13) Heneman, R.L. and Gresham, M.T (2013) *The Effects of Changes in The Nature of Work on*.
- 14) Hersey, P and Blanchard, K. H (2014). *Management of Organizational Behaviour: Utilizing Human Resources*. Prentice Hall, Eagle wood cliffs, New Jersey.
- 15) Hocker, J.L. and W.W. Wilmot, (2011). *Interpersonal Conflict*. 4th Edn. The McGraw-Hill Companies Inc., USA
- 16) Jones, G.R., J.M. Gorge and C.W.L. Hill, 2014. *Contemporary Management*. McGrawHill, Boston,
- 17) Kambo and Tromp (2014). *Research Met Heads of Department in Humanities and Education*. Eldoret: Zap chancy Research Consultants and Publishers
- 18) Kerr, S (2008). *On the Folly of Rewarding A, while hoping for B*. Academy of Management, U.S.A Chicago
- 19) Kirega, V.P.G. (2015). *Kampala City Handbook, Gava Associated Services*, Kampala Uganda.
- 20) Kombo, B. & Tromp, T, (2015) 'Market Evaluation tests and FASB statement 33 Disclosures: A re- examination', Journal of Accounting Research, (Supplement).